

Supplementary Material

for

“Factors Affecting Sound Quality in Acoustically Transparent Hearing Devices,”

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S.1 Additional Figures

Figure S.1: Resulting quality ratings for all experiments by scene. Horizontal red lines indicate the median, boxes indicate the interquartile ranges, whiskers span data points within 1.5 times the interquartile range, crosses show outliers. Colors as well as initials below the bottom panel indicate the used stimuli. Line styles indicate the number/position of sound sources and the filling of the boxplots indicate the scene type as denoted in the legend at the bottom.

Figure S.2: Rating differences between $indDF$ and $indDFdel$ for each subject (indicated by subject number at the left side) showing the distribution across scenes. Left panel: Rating differences obtained from subject results. Right panel: Rating differences obtained from model results. In both panels, positive values indicate a better perceived quality with the $indDF$ condition (i.e., without delay).

Figure S.3: Resulting quality ratings for Experiment 1a (without reference) by condition and scene. The top panel contains results for scenes using the speech stimulus, the middle panel for scenes using the jazz stimulus, the bottom panel for scenes with multiple sound sources (left to right: cafeteria, kitchen, nature, paneldiscussion). Horizontal red lines indicate the median, boxes indicate the interquartile ranges, whiskers span data points within 1.5 times the interquartile range, crosses show outliers. Colors indicate the used stimulus, line styles the number/position of sound sources and the filling of the boxplots indicate the scene type as denoted in the legend in Fig. S.1.

Experiment 1b

Figure S.4: Resulting quality ratings for Experiment 1b (with reference) by condition and scene. The top panel contains results for scenes using the speech stimulus, the middle panel for scenes using the jazz stimulus, the bottom panel for scenes with multiple sound sources (left to right: cafeteria, kitchen, nature, paneldiscussion). Horizontal red lines indicate the median, boxes indicate the interquartile ranges, whiskers span data points within 1.5 times the interquartile range, crosses show outliers. Colors indicate the used stimulus, line styles the number/position of sound sources and the filling of the boxplots indicate the scene type as denoted in the legend in Fig. S.1

Experiment 2

Figure S.5: Resulting quality ratings for Experiment 2 by condition and scene. The top panel contains results for scenes using the speech stimulus, the middle panel for scenes using the jazz stimulus, the bottom panel for scenes with multiple sound sources (left to right: cafeteria, kitchen, nature, paneldiscussion). Horizontal red lines indicate the median, boxes indicate the interquartile ranges, whiskers span data points within 1.5 times the interquartile range, crosses show outliers. Colors indicate the used stimulus, line styles the number/position of sound sources and the filling of the boxplots indicate the scene type as denoted in the legend in Fig. S.1

S.2 Subject Identifiers

For brevity, subjects were referred to using subject numbers 'S1' to 'S13' throughout the paper. Numbers were assigned based on the median rating difference between conditions *indDF* and *genDF*, i.e., subject S1 showed the smallest and subject S13 the largest benefit of using the respective individual TRCF. Subject numbers translate to original subject identifiers as used by the Hearpiece database [31] as seen in Tab. S.1.

Table S.1: Subject numbers and corresponding subject identifiers from the Hearpiece database.

Subject Number	Subject Identifier
S01	'ER07ED05'
S02	'EL08RD06'
S03	'ER09US30'
S04	'AU05RD24'
S05	'HM08CO04'
S06	'NK07ER02'
S07	'EK06AS04'
S08	'OF05UD28'
S09	'NE06RG13'
S10	'ITA4'
S11	'MI08LF31'
S12	'CH09US24'
S13	'ER06PH18'

S.3 Used Measurement Repetitions

The repetition used to compute the TRCFs and the test-repetition used for the simulation of the hearing device (in Experiment 2) was always repetition 3. Repetitions that were not used for the computation of the individual equalization filters (see Tab. S.2) were chosen manually to avoid obvious flaws.

Table S.2: Measurement repetitions that were not used to compute individual equalization filters.

Subject Number	Subject Identifier	Unused Repetitions
S02	'EL08RD06'	1
S01	'ER07ED05'	1
S05	'HM08CO04'	1
S09	'NE06RG13'	4

S.4 TRCFs

Transfer functions from which TRCFs were computed were first smoothed (1 ERB) to decrease perceptually irrelevant spectral detail. TRCFs were computed in the frequency domain through spectral division of the smoothed transfer functions. A minimum phase impulse response with a length of 256 samples (32 samples ramp out using a hann window).

S.5 Equalization Filters

Equalization filters of length $N=356$ samples were computed as described by [13] with regularization parameters $\beta = 1$ and $\lambda = 0.1$. The parameter for acausality management was chosen as $d_h = 22$. Before application of the equalization filters, an 8th order Butterworth lowpass filter with cut-off frequency 20,045 Hz was applied.

S.6 Scenes

The anechoic scenes and their reverberant equivalents were presented at 65 dB SPL, the complex scenes were presented at the level of the recording seen in Tab. S.3:

Table S.3: Recorded level of the four complex acoustic scenes.

Scene	Level [dB SPL]
Cafeteria	73.9
Kitchen	71.5
Nature	59.7
Paneldiscussion	63.7

S.7 Headphone Equalization

Headphone equalization filters were designed to have a length of 4096 samples and include 186 acausal filter taps.

S.8 Condition Abbreviations

To facilitate looking up condition abbreviations, a list of conditions can be found in Tab. S.4 for Experiment 1 and Tab. S.5 for Experiment 2.

Table S.4: Abbreviations used for conditions in Experiment 1.

Abbreviation	Long Version
<i>OpenEar</i>	HRTF to open ear (reference condition)
<i>indFF</i>	individual free-field TRCF
<i>indDF</i>	individual diffuse-field TRCF
<i>indSM</i>	individual scene-matched TRCF
<i>genDF</i>	generic diffuse-field TRCF
<i>halfDF</i>	half the gain computed for <i>genDF</i>
<i>indDF</i>	individual diffuse-field TRCF, but frequencies > 500 Hz are delayed by 6 ms
<i>protDF</i>	prototype TRCF (one TRCF chosen for each of three subgroups of subjects with similar <i>indDF</i> TRCFs)

Table S.5: Abbreviations used for conditions in Experiment 2.

Abbreviation	Long Version
<i>OpenEar</i>	HRTF to open ear (reference condition)
<i>genDF</i>	[from Experiment 1] generic diffuse-field TRCF
<i>indOpSD</i>	individual equalization, open-fit device, short (1 ms) delay
<i>indOpLD</i>	individual equalization, open-fit device, long (6 ms) delay
<i>genOpLD</i>	generic equalization, open-fit device, long (6 ms) delay
<i>bbOpLD</i>	broad-band level adaptation, open-fit device, long (6 ms) delay
<i>indClSD</i>	individual equalization, closed-fit device, short (1 ms) delay
<i>indClLD</i>	individual equalization, closed-fit device, long (6 ms) delay
<i>genClLD</i>	generic equalization, closed-fit device, long (6 ms) delay
<i>bbOpClLD</i>	broad-band level adaptation, closed-fit device, long (6 ms) delay